

**INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE
QUALITY OF EDUCATION ASSESSMENT SYSTEM**

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Abstract: The criteria for rating higher education institutions in developed nations, as well as the criteria for defining the national ranking of higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan, are analyzed and compared in this thesis. The flaws in the national rating system are discussed, as well as solutions.

Keywords: university rankings, evaluation criteria, rating indicators.

The rating is a way of measuring the quality of education in higher education institutions, and it is intended to provide information on the prestige of educational institutions to educational service customers, such as students, staff, and educational authorities. The ranking is based on a set of indicators that indicate the university's activities or current areas of education and specialties, and it establishes the university's place in the educational system. A rating is a number that expresses the superiority of one educational institution over another and is frequently derived as a conditional integral indication based on a number of individual factors. The purpose of the ranking is to improve the quality of educational services:

- the expansion and advancement of the educational services market;

- the objective of the educational system is to offer authorities, employees, parents, and students with information on the authority of educational institutions.
- Based on past experience, the rating is primarily used to evaluate the three types of indicators listed below:
 - Evaluation of performance indicators;
 - evaluation of indicators describing the current situation of the educational institution;
 - evaluation of indicators obtained through the institution's internal capability.
- A special place in this is given to the assessment of the conditions created for students to receive quality education, the indicators of employment of students in their specialties.

The methods for arranging and calculating educational institution rankings are varied, and they are strongly tied to country education systems and methods of evaluating higher education. A number of international countries, including the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, Poland, the Netherlands, Spain, Japan, China, Russia, and Ukraine, are now rich in determining and applying educational institution ratings. Their current ranking systems are based on various methodologies dependent on the educational system's peculiarities.

In the United States, rankings are based on three categories of quality indicators: student achievement, faculty achievement, and the university's academic promise. These indicators are converted into ratings using the weighting and aggregate approach. In the United Kingdom, the media determines the rating based on statistical data. Scientific work is also included in the list of indicators. One of the most important factors is consumer perceptions of the educational institution. The German rating system, which determines the ranking of specialties, is primarily developed for school graduates. As a result,

universities are classified as good, average, or awful. The evaluation is based on information about the universities and the cities in which they are located, the student population, fundamental course and training information, employment, the labor market, and faculty and student opinions.

In Poland, university rankings are done on a case-by-case basis, taking into consideration their unique qualities (ranking of universities, ranking of private universities, ranking of creative universities). The results of the previous year's rating are also factored into the ranking. Private institutions are ranked based on surveys completed directly within the university as well as surveys conducted among employers and professors.

In Japan, university rankings are based on three factors: instructional activities, research activities, and development contributions. Student polls have become increasingly popular in recent years.

Since 2001, a ranking of Russian higher education institutions has been conducted. Currently, there are two types of rating models: the Ministry of Education's rating and the media's rating. The rating in the first model is based on expert opinion and statistics, but employers' opinions are given less weight. The second model is more self-contained, although it lacks a strong scientific foundation. A nongovernmental rating organization was developed to take into account the beneficial characteristics of these two approaches.

To improve the quality of education in Uzbekistan's higher education institutions, to identify gaps, and to promote competitiveness on the basis of assessment and comparison of education quality in Uzbekistan's higher education institutions. The State Testing Center under the Cabinet of Ministers is responsible for determining the ranking of higher education institutions. The center annually provides the Government with analytical information on the development of higher education in the country on the basis of the currently approved methodology for compiling ratings.

The teaching staff of the top 300 higher education institutions in the world with the level of foreign higher education institutions (PhD) at the level of foreign higher education institutions (POD) share, level of teaching quality, number of textbooks and manuals published by teachers of higher education institutions during the year, share of foreign teachers and foreign students, and exchange programs with foreign higher education institutions are all included in the index of teaching quality. The number of areas of education (specialties) taught in a foreign language, the level of understanding of foreign languages and information and communication technologies, and the amount of laboratory and auxiliary equipment use in the educational process are all factors to consider.

As a result, credit technology is at the heart of international education integration. Scientific and technical progress had achieved its pinnacle by the second half of the twentieth century. The integration and cooperation of scientists and researchers from many countries, as well as higher education institutions, is clearly necessary for the advancement of scientific technology. Schools will be able to self-assess and identify current problems, and parents will get the information they need about their children's education as a result of this.

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